

A STUDY OF JOB SATISFACTION AMONG HIGH SCHOOL TEACHERS IN WEST BENGAL

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Abstract- The purpose of this study was to explore job satisfaction of high school teachers working in the high schools in West Bengal. The sample of 200 secondary school teachers was taken randomly from Nadia, Malda and Bankura district for this research study. The Job Satisfaction Scale (2013) developed by Dr. Meera Dixit was used for statistical analysis. For data analysis t-test was used. This study revealed that the male high school teachers have more job satisfaction than female high school teachers since the mean score of male is 187.11 and female is 180.34. The rural high school teachers have more job satisfaction with mean score 187.83 than the urban high school teachers which is 179.62. The Govt. high school teachers have more job satisfaction than Private high school teachers since the mean score of Govt. high school teachers being 191.09 is higher than that of Private high school teachers being 176.26.

Key Words: Job satisfaction, School teachers, gender, locality of school.

Introduction:

School education in developing countries like India, is a very demanding factor. It is a powerful driver of development to any nation. It prepares the way to develop the future generation with employment, innovation, social protection and poverty reduction. But in reality the slogan 'Education for All' still remains a far dream. Teachers are trying their best to grow the new generation mentally, physically, emotionally and academically and also motivating them to be independent.

Challenges in education increases day by day and teachers remain responsible for students' knowledge acquisition and skill oriented education. The National Education Policy 2020 focuses on the core values and principles to be developed besides improvement of critical thinking and problem solving in students. In this fast moving educational environment, teachers need high level of satisfaction otherwise educational goal cannot be fulfilled. A dissatisfied teacher will not be able to perform according to the policy makers. In previous studies it was revealed that the teachers remain interested to teach their students effectively only when they are satisfied with their jobs (Nigama, et.al., 2018).

Job Satisfaction:

Job satisfaction is not run by any single factor but it is a combination of physiological, psychological and environmental circumstances that leads an employee towards satisfaction with present job. In workplace it is a very essential factor to any employee as it acts as motivation and work productivity. Some conditions like adequate salary, job security and promotion opportunity, friendly management, co-workers' cooperation, healthy environment, etc. increase employees' satisfaction.

Teaching is a stressful profession and teachers go through various types of activities in keeping in the view of students' overall development. In this profession, pleasure in work and positive attitude to their profession is a very urgent element. It is one of the most important factors influencing teachers' relations to students (Van den Berg, 2002). There are numbers of factors affecting teachers' job satisfaction. Their satisfaction is depending on some factors like salary, poor benefits poor relationship with colleagues, students and parents and promotion opportunities lack of decision-making opportunities (Gedefaw, 2012).

Review related literature:

Raj, T & Lalita (2013) studied on job satisfaction of government and private school teachers and found no significant difference between male, female and government, private school teachers. Satvinderpal (2011) investigated teacher's job satisfaction and occupational stress and found that male teachers are more satisfied and less stressed as compared to female teachers. Nigama, K et.al (2018) found that only when teachers are satisfied with their job, effective teaching is possible. Demirdag (2015) studied on teachers' self-efficacy and job satisfaction of middle school teachers

in USA and it was found that there was non-significant and negative correlation between self-efficacy and job satisfaction of teachers.

Objectives:

The present study aims to investigate with the following objectives

- 1) To study the level of job satisfaction among high school teachers of West Bengal
- 2) To study if there is any significant difference of job satisfaction with gender variation
- 3) To study if there is any significant difference of job satisfaction with locality of school
- 4) To study if there is any significant difference of job satisfaction with types of school

Hypotheses:

Following the above objectives, the investigator stated the hypotheses below:

H01: There is no significant difference in job satisfaction of high school teachers with male and female gender variations

H02: There is no significant difference in job satisfaction of high school teachers with rural and urban variations

H03: There is no significant difference in job satisfaction of high school teachers with government and private variations.

Variables

The variables chosen for the present study are

- 1) Dependable variable- job satisfaction
- 2) Independent Variable- high school teachers

Population and sample

For the present study, the investigator targeted secondary school teachers of West Bengal state. From the target population a total 200 sample was taken for the present study. Following the simple random Sampling method 200 teachers were taken from different high schools from Nadia, Malda and Bankura district of West Bengal State.

Methods: The present work is a descriptive study investigating if teachers’ job satisfaction differed significantly to a group of variables of gender of teachers, locality of schools and types of school. Factors like Salary, Service Conditions and Promotion, Satisfaction with Authorities, Social Status and Family Welfare, Rapport with Students Relationship with Co-worker and Plans and Policies of Institution were the main finding aspects of the investigator.

Research Tool:

To analyse the job satisfaction of high school teachers of different levels, the investigator used Job Satisfaction Scale (2013) developed by Dr. Meera Dixit.

Data Analysis:

H₀₁ : There is no significant difference in job satisfaction of high school teachers with male and female gender variations.

Table – 1

Difference between male and female high school teachers in job satisfaction

Male High School Teachers			Female High School Teachers			MD	Df	SE _D	t-value	Significance
n ₁	Mean	SD	n ₂	Mean	SD					
100	187.11	16.37	100	180.34	17.81	6.77	198	2.42	2.80*	Sig. at 0.01 level

*t-criterion value at 0.01 level is 2.60 for df 198.

Interpretation : There is significant difference between the mean scores in job satisfaction of male and female high school teachers as the t-value of 2.80 is greater than the t-criterion value of 2.60 at 0.01 level for df 198. Hence the null hypothesis H₀₁ is rejected and the alternative hypothesis H₁ is accepted. The male high school teachers have more job satisfaction than female high school teachers since the mean score of male high school teachers being 187.11 is higher than that of female high school teachers being 180.34.

H₀₂ : There is no significant difference in job satisfaction of high school teachers with rural and urban variations.

Table – 2

Difference between rural and urban high school teachers in job satisfaction

Rural High School Teachers	Urban High School Teachers	MD	Df	SE _D	t-value	Significance
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n ₁	Mean	SD	n ₂	Mean	SD					
100	187.83	17.61	100	179.62	15.92	8.21	198	2.37	3.46*	Sig. at 0.01 level

*t-criterion value at 0.01 level is 2.60 for df 198.

Interpretation : There is significant difference between the mean scores of job satisfaction of rural and urban high school teachers as the t-value of 3.46 is greater than the t-criterion value of 2.60 at 0.01 level for df 198. Hence the null hypothesis H_{02} is rejected and the alternative hypothesis H_2 is accepted. The rural high school teachers have more job satisfaction than urban high school teachers since the mean score of rural high school teachers being 187.83 is higher than that of urban high school teachers being 179.62.

H₀₃ : There is no significant difference in job satisfaction of high school teachers with government and private variations.

Table – 3

Difference between government and private high school teachers in job satisfaction

Govt. High School Teachers			Private High School Teachers			MD	Df	SE _D	t-value	Significance
n ₁	Mean	SD	n ₂	Mean	SD					
100	191.09	16.17	100	176.26	14.58	14.83	198	2.18	6.81*	Sig. at 0.01 level

*t-criterion value at 0.01 level is 2.60 for df 198.

Interpretation:

There is significant difference between the mean scores of job satisfaction of government and private high school teachers as the t-value of 6.81 is greater than the t-criterion value of 2.60 at 0.01 level for df 198. Hence the null hypothesis H_{03} is rejected and the alternative hypothesis H_3 is accepted. The Govt. high school teachers have more job satisfaction than Private high school teachers since the mean score of Govt. high school teachers being 191.09 is higher than that of Private high school teachers being 176.26.

Result:

The present study revealed that there is significant difference between the job satisfaction levels of male and female teachers with t-value 2.80 is greater than the t-criterion value of 2.60 at 0.01 level. A significant difference is found between rural and urban teachers while t-value is found 3.46. It is also inferred that there is a difference between the job satisfaction between government and private school teachers and government high school teachers are more satisfied as compared to private teachers while t-value is 6.81.

Discussion:

The present study reveals the job satisfaction levels of high school teachers of West Bengal district with gender of teachers, types of school and locality of school variables. From the result of the study it is found that there is difference of job satisfaction of these three variables. Male teachers are more satisfied than the female teachers. Again rural school teachers are more satisfied as compare to urban teachers. There is also a clear difference found between government and private school teachers while government teachers are more satisfied than the private teachers. There may be the causes of difference with salary, physical facilities, communication, job security and satisfaction with authorities.

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